

REVIEW ARTICLE

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Advancement in UV-Visible-IR camouflage textiles for concealment of defence surveillance against multidimensional combat backgrounds

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Abstract

Target detection of defence technologies is being rapidly upgraded with modern surveillance technologies. The latest techniques of surveillance are already being implemented for defence applications. Self-protection and hiding from opposing forces are the key principles for the protection of special team in defence. Camouflage textiles aim to create confusing objects for target detection of military personnel. These textiles are applied for military protection such as clothing, weapons, vehicles and location hiding nets/tents. The urgent need for camouflage textiles has been formulated with a technical solution and implementation of the right camouflage materials for concealment of defence target signature against dry leaves, green leaves and tree bark-woodland combat background; water-marine combat background; sand-desertland combat background; stone-stoneland combat background; snow-snowland combat background; sky combat background; ice-iceland combat background; and concrete-concreteland combat background (DGTWSICB) in ultraviolet-visible-infrared (UV-Vis-IR) spectrums. This hypothesis of optical and surveillance engineering, digital imaging and hyperspectral imaging has been coalesced for the advancement of UV-Vis-IR-DGTWSICB camouflage textile technology. The principle of camouflage engineering has been approached by broader spectrum probes in UV-Vis-IR rather than Vis ranges only. Furthermore, camouflage materials, camouflage weapon designs, and formulations of camouflage textiles have been proposed for multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. The electromagnetic spectrum, reflection, electron energy, photonic signal and imaging mechanism in UV-Vis-IR have been presented for optical engineering of concealment, detection, recognition and identification of target signature against DGTWSICB. The spectrum relationship of camouflage materials and DGTWSICB materials has been illustrated and compared in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. Camouflage material design, method design and spectral design; textile colorants and technologies; adaptive camouflage; techniques for camouflage textile assessment for digital camera and hyperspectral camera imaging; image processing techniques; and a hierarchical model have been demonstrated for augmentation of camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-IR illumination. Therefore, the anticipated design of camouflage textiles may enhance high-performance innovation for modern surveillance of military protection related to digital camera, hyperspectral camera and radar. This hypothesis includes advanced guidelines for the advanced design of camouflage textiles for multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. The challenges, limitations, innovation and defence applications of camouflage engineering for multidimensional combat backgrounds have been coalesced for concealment, detection, recognition and identification of defence target signature.

Keywords Camouflage textiles, Camouflage engineering, Color engineering, Camouflage materials-methods-spectral design, Combat backgrounds, Camouflage assessment, UV-Vis-IR, Defence protection, Target signature

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Introduction

Surveillance technologies in visible range camouflage and detection are practiced by military professionals. Modern battlefield has been a great challenge due to advanced surveillance of broad electromagnetic spectrums in ultraviolet–visible–near infrared (UV–Vis–NIR) ranges (Lu et al., 2022; Vitalija et al., 2008). Camouflage textiles designate an artificial masking process of target objects with combat backgrounds (CBs) by adaptation of pattern, texture and chromatic characteristics (Sujit et al., 2013). Concealment can be defined as the perceptive interface between the observer/digital camera/hyperspectral camera and target signature by which camouflage textiles are not visualized to detect the antagonistic (enemy) of the opposing team. Camouflage textiles would allow an object to blend into its surrounding combat environment by the optical mechanism of color matching or luminosity. The scale of concealment and detection is identified by its degree of adaptability which means the capability of an adapting object (appearance) to match its CB. The concealment of camouflage textiles can be designed by means of a spectrum probe under specific CB and/or multidimensional CB environments (Jiri et al., 2011). Camouflage textiles are the general practice by defence professionals for hiding weapons, locations and humans from opposition teams. Presently, surveillance technologies have been advanced in extended electromagnetic spectrums in UV–Vis–NIR.

There is an enormous limitation of technologies to fulfill the current requirements of camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs such as dry leaves, green leaves, and tree bark–woodland combat background; water–marine combat background; sand–desertland combat background; stone–stoneland combat background; snow–snowland combat background; sky combat background; ice–iceland combat background; and concrete–concreteland combat background (DGTWSICB). It is necessary to improve camouflage textiles for target concealment and protection of defence professionals against multidimensional CBs–DGTWSICB in the UV–Vis–IR spectrum (Lu et al., 2022).

Figure 1 depicts the brief application field of camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage weapon design. Figure 2 shows the whole advancement in UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles.

Overview of camouflage textile design and engineering of advancement

Camouflage materials and camouflage assessment have become a vibrant segment of defence research for the protection of special teams in defence who are always playing with the enemy as part of the daily responsibilities of defence profession, and this is an ongoing research headache to the defence and color scientist. There is an enormous lack in standardization of camouflage materials and methodology for the right concealment of the

Fig. 1 Applications of camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs–DGTWSICB in the UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Fig. 2 Overview of the article on advancement in UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles

target signature. An overview of deceiving material selection for camouflage textile formulation and methodological steps of camouflage textile assessment has been demonstrated for the concealment of target signature against CB. The properties of UV-Vis-IR reflection of materials, pigmentation, nanomaterials, thermochromic dyes, thermal insulation and synthetic dyes have been critically discussed in terms of camouflage material properties and their advancement for suitability of defence textile applications. The camouflage mechanism of concealment, detection, recognition and identification (CDRI) of defence target signature has been represented by the chromatic appearance of the target object and CB, digital camera/hyperspectral camera assessment and image processing technique. Therefore, a hierarchical model for camouflage textile formulation and assessment of CDRI has been proposed for simultaneous spectrums in UV-Vis-IR/specific spectrums in UV/Vis/IR for defence applications against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. Optical parameters in UV-Vis-IR are the critical challenge for developing camouflage textiles against multidimensional combat environments. There

are enormous factors that need to be considered to develop a camouflage product, but the core technologies of camouflage engineering are very limited in the literature. There is scope for broaden research for the development of camouflage technologies. This manuscript coalesces a whole optical meaning of camouflage engineering whole controllable and uncontrollable parameters of camouflage engineering to achieve concealment across UV-Vis-IR spectra to meet the multidimensional demands of combat environments. The author coalesces whole parameters, material engineering and color engineering for the optical design of UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles. The optical phenomena have been represented to conceal camouflage textiles against combat environments.

Optical engineering of camouflage textile design against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB

Figure 3a shows the rough surface design, applicable for the bark camouflage of trees. Figure 3b signifies the disruptive camouflage pattern, applicable for the multi-color effect or tree bark effect. Figure 3c remarks on the

Fig. 3 Camouflage textile patented, patterned and designed for chromatic and achromatic matching against the CB environment

camouflage design of the broken lines, applicable to the design of the leaf of the tree. Figure 3d shows the camouflage design of the human body, the design is applicable for versatile CB. Figure 3e shows the camouflage design with the repeated unit of animal, applicable for woodland CB. Figure 3f reflects the chromatic matching between printed fabric and woodland CB. In Fig. 1, the design of camouflage textile has been patented in visible ranges having limitations with multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB and broader electromagnetic spectrums. Figure 1 prioritizes the different patterns for the design of camouflage textiles against selected CB. These patterns generate the idea about the chromatic and achromatic properties of camouflage textiles against selected CB. Current camouflage textiles (Don, 1989; Floyd, 2016; Marybeth, 1989; Ramli et al., 2012; Rodney, 2007; Sujit et al., 2013; Thomas, 1987) have been augmented in Vis and limited spectrum probe in IR, but the reflection is still visible due to the reflectance of CB materials such

as leaves, bark, branches, grasses and other background materials. Camouflage textile particularly depends on chromatic adaptation with CB in terms of spectral reflectance and its variations. The reflection profile of DGTWSICB materials is the demanding factor for the development of real concealment of camouflage textiles in UV–Vis–IR spectrums against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB (Goudarzi et al., 2014; Lu et al., 2022; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2020). Spectral reflectivity is the optical principle for chromatic and achromatic deviation of target signature. For example, marine camouflage textiles are influenced by the color of water and optical properties in terms of background (Chen et al., 2010). The reflection profile of every CB differs in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. Reflectance of woodland CB is a matter of “chlorophyll” referred to the chromatic adaptation of a green color (fresh leaves) background (Hui & Jianchun, 2007). Textile dyes such as vat, disperse, reactive, sulphur, acid, thermochromic materials, electrochromic materials,

IR reflective pigments, metal oxides such as iron oxide, and nanoparticles such as titanium dioxide are being practiced with textile coloration and coating/printing processes for the development of camouflage textiles. The combination of the right camouflage materials and the development of demanded camouflage textiles have been limited in multidimensional spectrums and CBs. It is necessary to establish actual deceiving material formulation and standard process for the concealment of the target signature in terms of reflection, gloss, texture and color with CB in UV–Vis–IR (Goudarzi et al., 2014; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a). Spectral reflectance between the target signature and surrounding CB of geographical regions should match for the concealment of the defence target. The evaluation process of concealment and its accuracy is also considered a complicated process of assessment due to the time-consuming and labor-intensive way of field trialing. Spectral and photographic analyses in UV–Vis–IR are the optical advancement for CDRI of target signature against CBs–DGTWSICB (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Md Anwar Hossain, 2022; Kang et al., 2016; Vitalija et al., 2008).

Modeling of exponential pictograph

An exponential relationship is used to fit the optical phenomenon of camouflage materials against combat materials. The relation signifies the suitability of material applications, formulation of material and camouflage coloration. A software-generated value of γ and R^2 has been shown in an exponential relationship. The exponential model represents the optical parameters of camouflage physics such as electron energy, photonic response, reflection, irradiance, optical character in UV–Vis–IR spectrums, optical interference in CBs and imaging versus CDRI prediction in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. The exponential model partially predicts the outcome of R^2 between the value of 0 to 1. Hence, the exponential variation refers to any value of $1 - R^2$. R^2 means the relative predictive power. The nearest value of 1 determines a more accurate prediction of the outcome. In this manuscript, material properties in UV–Vis–IR spectrums have been reviewed and parallelly modeled for the development of UV–Vis–IR camouflage material. The values of reflection percentages have been shown for the remarkable graphical representation. This optical signification has no specific target to make a specific value of R^2 . R^2 values are the outcomes of material properties in UV–Vis–IR spectrums in existing literature. In this subsequent graphical and exponential hypothesis, there is no matter of control the R^2 value and/or make \pm of R^2 value which is the graphical state to simplify the correlation of optical design in terms of camouflage materials and combat materials. Every

value of R^2 is 0 to 1. “0” identifies a far distance from the exponential plot for actual probability; oppositely, “1” identifies the exact matching with the exponential plot in the graph for actual probability. Euler’s number, $e=2.71828$; the constant value represents the exponential function and the speed of increasing or decreasing trend of specific material. The exponential curve signifies the spectral relationship of camouflage material and the materials of CB in UV–Vis–IR spectrums which typically signifies the probability of material for camouflage in UV–Vis–IR under standard temperature and humidity for laboratory scale camouflage assessment. In this article, it is difficult to clarify to indicate the exact temperature and humidity due to the limitations of the review and literature. However, the proposed technologies of camouflage engineering and color engineering for processing textile materials were experimentally tested and presented in different published articles by the sole author, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, scientist; affiliated with RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia, in 2020–2023 (Hossain, 2023h). The final technical data and their optical effects of different climatic conditions are also remarked on, shown, and discussed for color engineering, camouflage engineering, image engineering, target signature and CBs. The nearest value of R^2 correlates with the maximum suitability and probability of camouflage materials against selected CBs. Exponential techniques were used to represent the concise reviewed data for the reader’s clarification in addition to original data and supplementary information under the limitation of review and idea generation for the next stage of research which also experimented by the author for more clarification and signification for camouflage textiles through the techniques of camouflage physics, color engineering, camouflage textiles and defence technologies of CDRI.

The framework of the innovative approach for UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles

The key contributions of camouflage engineering in UV–Vis–IR spectrums have been approached in terms of nine phases of advancement for camouflage textiles. This study has found a new direction of camouflage chemistry and camouflage physics focusing on camouflage material design, method design, CBs–DGTWSICB and extended spectrums which are beyond of existing idea and invention of present literature. This hypothesis of camouflage design is applicable to high-performance camouflage research for defence protection in digital imaging and hyperspectral imaging.

1. Advancement phase-1, illumination principle for CDRI of target signature in UV–Vis–IR spectrums against multidimensional CBs–DGTWSICB.

2. Advancement phase 2, UV–Vis-IR engineering for camouflage textile formulation against CBs-DGTWSICB.
3. Advancement phase 3, exponential relationships of multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB in UV–Vis-IR spectrums.
4. Advancement phase 4, the hypothesis of camouflage textile design in UV–Vis-IR illumination against CBs-DGTWSICB.
5. Advancement phase 5, material design for camouflage textile coloration against CBs-DGTWSICB under UV–Vis-IR spectrums.
6. Advancement phase 6, method design for CDRI measurement of target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB under UV–Vis-IR spectrums.
7. Advancement phase 7, significant advancement of camouflage textiles against modern defence surveillance in UV–Vis-NIR spectrums.
8. Advancement phase 8, the principle of optical approach for camouflage textile coloration for concealment against digital camera imaging/hyperspectral imaging in UV–Vis-IR spectrums.
9. Advancement phase 9, the hierarchical model for camouflage textile formulation and assessment of CDRI against CBs-DGTWSICB.

Advancement phase 1, illumination principle for CDRI of target signature in UV–Vis-IR against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB

The optical mechanism of CDRI in UV–Vis-IR camouflaging, chromatic appearance, spectral frequency, electron energy versus photonic signal for digital camera imaging and hyperspectral camera imaging have been demonstrated by the ‘reflection engineering’ and ‘imaging theory’ in the vein of wavelength-reflection-electron energy-photonic signal. Figure 4 and Eqs. 1–7; CDRI principle has been illustrated according to established theories

of wavelength-reflection-electron energy-photonic signal such as Einstein’s theory of energy (Okun, 2006), Broglie relation of wavelength (Masanoro, 2020) (Broglie, 1987), Snell’s law of reflection (Cole, 1973; Sun et al., 2005) and photon energy of Max Planck (Marburger, 2011). Illumination in the form of energy creates a photonic signal for surveillance and imaging of the target signature against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB.

Principle of optical engineering for CDRI in UV–Vis-IR spectrums

From Eqs. 1 and 2, we can find the difference between the angular momentum of the target signature and CB material-DGTWSICB for CDRI of the target signature.

$$\lambda = h/P = h/mv \tag{1}$$

where λ = wavelength of the electron; Planck’s constant, $h = 6.6 \times 10^{-34}$ kgm²/s; P is the momentum of target CB materials or target signature; the P value manipulates the value of λ in UV–Vis-IR and chromatic appearance of target signature or target CB materials; m = mass of electron of target signature; and v = velocity of the electron. By putting the values of h , m , and v in Eq. 1, we can signify the wavelength. Wavelength in UV–Vis-IR spectrums controls spectral frequency-electron energy-photonic signal for chromatic and achromatic appearance/digital imaging/hyperspectral imaging of target signature against CB material-DGTWSICB.

$$P = \frac{m v}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} \tag{2}$$

where P is the electron angular momentum of the target signature, m is the mass of the electron of the target signature, v is the velocity of the electron of the target signature, and c is the velocity of the light. By putting the values of m , v , and c , we can find the angular momentum of the target signature at different CB locations.

Fig. 4 Illumination principle of digital camera/red, green, blue (RGB) imaging-hyperspectral camera imaging-UV–Vis-IR- CDRI for defence target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB

Optical principle of refractive index and reflection for CDRI in UV-Vis-IR spectrums

By putting the values of i and r in Eq. 3, we can find the refractive index of target CB and target signature.

$$n = \sin(i)/\sin(r) \quad (3)$$

where i is the angle of incidence and r is the angle of refraction.

From Eq. 3, the difference in angle of refraction (Δn) for CDRI can be determined using Eq. 4:

$$\Delta n = n_1 - n_2 \quad (4)$$

where n_1 and n_2 are the refractive index of target CB and target signature. By putting the values of n_1 and n_2 , we can signify the CDRI of the target signature against the surrounding background in UV-Vis-IR. The value of n_2 will be almost zero or infinitive when the target signature is high reflective or zero reflectance; hence, the target will be concealed against CB. The minimum/maximum value will identify the CDRI of the target signature against CB.

The spectral and imaging signal of CDRI depends on the velocity of light. From Eq. 5, the difference in velocity of light between CB and target materials for CDRI can be determined.

$$\Delta v = c/n_1 - c/n_2 \quad (5)$$

where c is the constant speed of light, c/n_1 determines the velocity of light of CB materials, n_1 is the value of the refractive index of CB materials, c/n_2 determines the velocity of light of target signature, and n_2 is the value of the refractive index of target signature.

Optical principle of electron energy and photon signal for CDRI in UV-Vis-IR spectrums

By determining the energy of the photon signal of target CB and target signature, we can indicate CDRI of the target signature against surrounding CB in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. When the difference of electron state between the target signature and target CB is nearest to zero or infinitive, the photon signal will follow the energy response to the camera sensor for imaging and spectral frequency of target OB. Therefore, the target signature will be concealed or confused against background materials, CBs-DGTWSICB. The higher energy difference for target CDRI, ΔE , as shown in Eq. 6 will signify the higher number of photons to the camera sensor for detection, recognition, and identification, respectively.

$$\Delta E = hc_1/\lambda - hc_2/\lambda \quad (6)$$

where Planck's constant, $h=6.6 \times 10^{-34}$ kgm²/s; λ is the wavelength of the electron; the term $h c_1/\lambda$ determines the energy of photon signal of target CB materials; c_1 is

the velocity of the light for imaging of CB materials; the term $h c_2/\lambda$ determines the energy of photon signal of target signature; and c_2 is the velocity of light for imaging of target signature.

Optical principle of spectral reflectance for CDRI in UV-Vis-IR spectrums

If the target signature shows zero reflection, the electron energy of the photon signal states at the rest position of acceleration. At rest position of an electron is considered for a target signature of zero reflection materials or low reflection materials, and a voltage difference is considered V volts. The wavelength for identifying CDRI can be determined by using the De Broglie equation of wavelength Eq. 7.

$$\lambda = h/P = h/mv = h/\sqrt{2 \text{ meV}} = \frac{6.6 \times 10^{-34}}{\sqrt{2 \times 9 \times 10^{-31} \times 1.6 \times 10^{-19} \times V}} \quad (7)$$

where Planck's constant, $h=6.6 \times 10^{-34}$ kgm²/s; the constant mass of the electron, $m=9.1 \times 10^{-31}$ kg; constant electron charge, $e=1.6 \times 10^{-19}$ C; and v is the velocity of electron energy carried by photon for creation of imaging signal.

For low-reflection/zero-reflection materials, the electron velocity (v) will be almost zero; and for high-reflection materials, the electron velocity (v) will be infinitive. Therefore, the spectral signal will not be detected for the chromatic appearance and the target signature will be denoted as concealed. Accordingly, detection, recognition and identification of the target signature will be signified by the specific value of the velocity of electron energy.

Advancement phase 2, UV-Vis-IR engineering for camouflage textile formulation against CBs-DGTWSICB

Optical principle of electron energy versus sun radiation for the design of UV-Vis-IR camouflage textiles

In Figs. 5a, b, an exponential graph has been illustrated to simplify the spectral relationship between electron energy and sun radiation in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. Here, the total energy of sunlight is classified into UV-Vis-IR spectrums: UV band, 200–400 nm stores 5% of the total energy; Vis band, 400–720 nm stores 45% of the total energy; and NIR band, 720–2500 nm stores 50% of the total energy (Wake & Brady, 1993). Ninety-nine percent of the sun radiates between 200 and 4000 nm in the chromatic condition of visible 'red ray'. Electron energy, E (eV) of sun radiation changes in UV-Vis-IR spectrums. The summarized data information has been cited in Table S1(a, b). The vibration of electron energy shown in Fig. 5a and sun radiation shown in Fig. 5b are

Fig. 5 An exponential relationship of wavelength versus electron energy, 100–10000 nm (a) and sun radiation, 250–2500 nm (b) in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

significantly higher in UV–Vis spectrums and dramatically decline in IR spectrums. Electrons of object-background (OB) materials combine with the photon from the light of the surveillance device to form chromatic intensity versus imaging of target OB materials. Electron energy and photonic combination generate the intensity/imaging of target OB in the different wavelengths of UV–Vis–IR. The flow of electron energy is almost constant in the entire spectrum of UV–Vis–IR; comparatively higher in UV, medium in Vis and lower in IR spectrums. Photon direction is a matter of altering trichromatic reflection to the imaging sensor. This optical condition of imaging is controlled by the electron energy of OB materials and its related interferences. Choosing the reflection matching materials with multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB for textile formulation may signify the target concealment in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. In optical engineering, the replacement of wavelength changes the electron energy from the target signature to the camera sensor. Electron energy creates a variation of refractive index, which alters the appearance of the target signature to the imaging sensor. Lower electron energy is the limitation of conventional ‘color matching theory’ in IR camouflaging. Hence, the reflection-changing materials may be an optical solution of IR camouflaging or simultaneous camouflaging in UV–Vis–IR spectrums for optical matching of target signature against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB (Cui, 2011; Hossain, 2023; Loebich, 1972).

Reflection versus chromatic signal for the formulation of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles

Snell’s law is much related illustration for reflectance characteristics of target OB. According to Snell’s law of reflection, the speed of light rays decreases when traveling to a refractive medium (Cole, 1973; Sun et al., 2005). The refractive indexes of the international commission on illumination (CIE)-RGB colors at different wavelengths in UV–Vis–IR are not similar. Such as the refractive index of red color is 1.50917 at wavelength 640 nm, yellow 1.51124 at wavelength 589 nm, green 1.51534 at

wavelength 509 nm, blue 1.51696 at wavelength 486 nm and violet 1.52136 at wavelength 434 nm. Illumination parameters such as refractive index, reflection angle (0° to 360°) and wavelength determine the chromatic signal of target signature and CBs-DGTWSICB to the sensor of digital camera and hyperspectral camera in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. Hence, the chromatic appearances of target OB are replaced when reflectance coefficients (0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0) are shifted as the spectrum probe shown in Fig. 6 (Sönke, 2016; Sun et al., 2005). In general, typical chromatic replacements have been remarked by the replacement of wavelength by the replacement of reflectance value by the replacement of reflection angle between the target signature and optical device. It is so tough to narrate exact optical parameters for camouflage engineering due to optical interference. Reflection coefficients are also related to OB properties in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. Surface gloss depends on surface smoothness or irregularity. Gloss is higher on smooth surfaces and lower on irregular surfaces (Md Anwar Hossain, 2022; Wake & Brady, 1993).

Geometrical theory of reflection for the design of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles against CBs-DGTWSICB

The key principle of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles is minimizing the difference in light scattering or radiating properties between the target signature and CBs-DGTWSICB. Hence, the concealment of camouflage textiles depicts a fake target to appear as an optical mechanism of artificial concealing with the opposition team (Tao et al., 2012). Sequentially, camouflage textiles are specified in terms of illumination of target signature and CBs. The angle of reflection depends on the direction of the incident light beam from OB. The ratio of speed difference of light striking denotes the refractive index of OB. The light obstacle is also a fact of camouflage objects as predicted by ‘geometrical ray theory’ when light passes through a tiny hole known as ‘diffraction’. This optical mechanism creates uneven shadow and reflection on the imaging device. Practically, light waves from sunlight

Fig. 6 Typical chromatic appearance (schematic) of six specified wavelengths (nm) in Vis (472 nm and 682 nm) and NIR (870 nm, 1036 nm, 1219 nm and 1273 nm) spectrums

and the camera sensor are not similar, so optical interference occurs when two overlapping of light from unlike sources. A maximum value of refractive index generates the high bending of light. Absorption is a process of transferring energy from the electromagnetic wave to the atom of the target signature and CB substances. The energy can create the excitation of electrons into a higher energy state, and it depends on the wavelength spectrums of light in UV–Vis–IR. Therefore, the absorption–transmission–reflection (ATR) of OB is the key principle behind the camouflage coloration. Optical scattering is an energy removal process of a light beam depending on the structural composition of OB. Optical transmission depicts the weakened absorption and scattering when OB states behind open space in a combat environment of CBs–DGTWSICB (Kulappurath, 2018; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2022).

Reflection principle for camouflage measurement in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Camouflage textiles are possible to be designed to have irregular chromatic combination, reflection matching and perforation of the surface under consideration of specific CB (Gunnar, 1976). The ATR of the chromophore group differs in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. The intensity of ATR creates chromatic variation (Sudhakar et al., 2008). The design of camouflage textiles is related to color, contrast, lightness, shape, texture and depth of object–background (OB) materials. The hyperspectral camera captures the color outlook of every pixel in the image of the target object and CB. The color difference between OB can be depicted by hue, chromatic and lightness. Spectral behavior and reflection properties of the target signature

at a specific wavelength are the key facts for camouflage textiles with any CB as light is simultaneously reflected from the target OB. Reflection of OB is highly influenced by natural illumination, inter-reflections of existing molecules in the atmosphere, air density and temperature differences. The perceived/imaging color and the measured actual color may have some differences. So there are limitations of accuracy for camouflage measurement in a laboratory rather than field trialing (Baumbach, 2012). CB has many reflectance spectra depending on the angle of light falling on the background and the angle of illumination of the digital camera/hyperspectral camera (Sönke, 2016).

Advancement phase 3, exponential relationships of multidimensional CBs–DGTWSICB in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Figures 7, 9, and 10 show the spectrum relationships of DGTWSICB such as woodland CB: grass/green leaves (Hossain, 2023aq; Leong, 2007) (Figs. 7a and 10c), dry leaves, tree bark (Asner, 1998; Hossain, 2023aq) (Figs. 7b and 10a, b), vegetation and deciduous tree (Leong, 2007) (Fig. 7c); snowland, iceland and marine CB: snow (Fig. 7d), ice (Fig. 7e) and water (Qunzhu et al., 1983) (Fig. 7f); desertland CB (Burkinshaw et al., 1996; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022c): sand (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022c; Winkelmann, 2015) (Fig. 7g, h) (Asner, 1998) (i); and sky and urban CB: sky (Bachmann et al., 2012) (Fig. 7j), red brick and concrete (Leong, 2007) (Fig. 7k). Spectral data information is summarised through published literature, a supporting information is attached in Table S1, c–m. Every exponential spectrum has been illustrated to represent a common

Fig. 7 Exponential relationship of multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB materials in UV-Vis-IR spectrums: (a) 700–1600 nm; (b) 500–2500 nm; (c) 300–1900 nm; (d) 400–1200 nm; (e) 400–1200 nm; (f) 400–1200 nm; (g) 400–1200 nm; (h) 2000–14,000 nm; (i) 500–2500 nm; (j) 300–1900 nm; (k) 300–1900 nm

spectral coefficient of CB in UV-Vis-IR (Hossain, 03 February 2023; Xu & Liang, 2001). These exponential spectra typically signify the expected spectra of camouflage materials under single/multidimensional

CBs-DGTWSICB. Spectral characteristics of individual CB need to be considered for camouflage coloration against single CB or simultaneous CB or adaptive CB under UV-Vis-IR spectrums.

Fig. 8 Spectral signals of high-reflection materials at 200–10,000 nm (a) and synthetic dyes at 350–950 nm (b) in UV–Vis–IR spectrums with the relationship of exponential coefficients

Advancement phase 4, hypothesis of camouflage textile design in UV–Vis–IR illumination against CBS-DGTWSICB

Optical principle of technical materials versus synthetic dyes for camouflage textiles in simultaneous spectrum probe

Figure 8a, b illustrates a general comparison of exponential relationships between high-reflection materials and synthetic dyes. Reviewed data are summarized and cited in Table S1 (o) (Cui, 2011). Figure 8a, aluminium, rhodium and titanium particle show an almost straight line in UV–Vis–IR spectrums as a sequence of aluminium > rhodium > titanium > copper > silver > gold. Such high-reflection materials may signify camouflage materials in UV–Vis–IR due to random/infinite photonic response to the imaging device. Figure 8b depicts the exponential relationships of synthetic dyes which

shows the completely reverse behavior in UV–Vis–NIR spectrums. Chrysoidine, orange 2 and lithol fast scarlet-rhodamine naphthol phthalein (RNP) are the synthetic dyes of the mono azo group; chrysophenine G is a synthetic dye of the diazo group; and flavophosphine is a dye of the acridine group. These groups of synthetic dyes are very common for textile coloration in terms of CB color matching in the Vis spectrum. Therefore, camouflage textile coloration in simultaneous spectrum probes needs to choose alternative materials rather than synthetic dyes only or technical formulation of synthetic dyes. The UV–Vis–IR spectrums of synthetic dyes and high-reflection materials have been classified as the low and high amplitude of the signal. Figure 8a, b in comparison, synthetic dyes are remarked as deviation of high amplitude, and high-reflection materials are signified as variation of low amplitude. Few high-reflection materials

Table 1 Summarised exponential relationship of electron energy/photonic response among multidimensional CB materials and materials for textile coloration in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Multidimensional CBs materials	Electron energy or photonic response	Materials for textile coloration (dyeing or coating or printing)	Electron energy or photonic response
Woodland	NIR > Vis > UV	Synthetic dyes (five different)	NIR > Vis > UV
Snowland	UV > Vis > NIR	Aluminium	UV = Vis = IR
Iceland	UV > Vis > NIR	Rhodium	Vis = IR
Marine	UV > Vis > NIR	Copper	IR > Vis > UV
Desertland	IR > Vis > UV	Titanium	IR > Vis > UV
Soil	IR > Vis > UV	Silver	IR > Vis > UV
Sky	UV > Vis > NIR	Gold	Vis = IR
Urban	NIR > Vis > UV	Shiny surface	UV = Vis = IR

have almost zero deviation of amplitude and hypothetically remarked as $UV = Vis = IR$ and $Vis = IR$ referred to Table 1. Electron density significantly decreases when spectral amplitude/intensity is in the negligible range (Sark, 2002; Shengyue et al., 2015). There is a possibility of capturing a minor deviation of the photonic signal to the imaging sensor in UV–Vis–NIR illumination. Accordingly, the reflectance profile of CB varies in the UV–Vis–NIR region (Hui & Jianchun, 2007). The reflection factors of CB such as tree branches, leaves, soil, rocks and water differ by 10–80% for the CDRI mechanism (Puzikova et al., 2008). The difference in reflection between the target object (camouflage textiles) and CB determines the chromatic adaptation (CIE RGB, L^* , a^* , b^*) versus CDRI. The reflection properties of CB are the parameters of CDRI for the target signature (Muzaffer & Yavuz, 2010). The threat of reflection is also related to the surrounding CB materials rather than specific known materials of CBs-DGTWSICB (Thomas, 1987). Therefore, the optical hypothesis of simultaneous spectrum probe camouflage textiles in UV–Vis–NIR ranges is critical due to the deviation of reflection phenomenon from signature and CBs.

In Figs. 7g, h, and i and 9; the NSSD material and aluminium may be coated on textile substances for the reflection matching against desertland CB (Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c). In Fig. 9b, c; laboratory and field trialing samples of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain have been shown for color matching for the concealment against desertland combat background. Figure 9b remarks on the concealing ability of silicon dioxide-coated textiles against desertland CB. Figure 9c signifies the concealing ability of aluminium-coated hollow fabric against desertland CB. In Fig. 10c, d; there is a reflection matching between chromium oxide-coated textiles and woodland combat material (green leaves). Chromium oxide material may be coated on textile material for concealment against woodland combat background (green

leaves) because of the symmetrical properties of synthetic chlorophyll and natural chlorophyll. In Fig. 10a, b, there is a deviation between the reflection of dry leaves and tree bark against chromium oxide-coated textiles due to the material properties of dry leaves and tree bark due to lack of chlorophyll existence (Hossain, 2023aq). In Figs. 7a–c, e, f, and 10g; NPND materials can be coated on textile materials for woodland camouflage textiles. Laboratory and field trialing samples of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain have been shown for color matching for the concealment against a woodland combat background. Figure 10e remarks on the concealment of Cr oxide-coated textiles against green grasses and stems against woodland materials. Figure 10f shows the deviation of color matching of Cr oxide-coated textiles against dry grasses and stems against woodland materials. Figure 10g signifies the deviation of color matching of Cr oxide-coated textiles against the simultaneous reflection of dry grasses, green grasses, dry stems, green stems, dry tree barks and dry tree leaves against woodland materials.

Optical principle of material design for camouflage textiles in simultaneous spectrum probe

In Fig. 11, Vis-IR coefficients of black color and high-reflection materials (shiny surface) are represented at similar pixel positions. A simultaneous photonic signal in Vis-IR is illustrated by the sum of Vis and IR amplitude. The data information has been attached in Table S1 (n). The variation of the photonic signal is significantly higher in Vis than in IR. Heat in the IR region increases the emissivity of OB and declines the reflectance of OB. This IR mechanism is responsible for minor photonic signals to remote sensing devices of digital imaging/hyperspectral imaging. In IR spectrums, the photonic response of black color is comparatively higher than in high-reflection materials as shown in amplitude. Oppositely, a photonic signal of black color is lower than high-reflection

Fig. 9 Exponential relationship of natural sand-based silicon dioxide (NSSD) and aluminium for desertland combat background from 400 to 700 nm (a), samples of NSSD-coated textiles (b), and aluminium-coated textiles (c) against desertland combat background

materials in Vis spectrums. Hence, the hypothesis states that the combination principle of such materials may signify simultaneous camouflage in UV–Vis–IR spectrums (Gao & Tian, 2018).

Optical principle of technical formulation of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles

UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles are proposed by treating them with metallic reflection materials such as aluminum, copper and zinc. Camouflage pigment such as chromium oxide has reflection properties like ‘chlorophyll’ for adaptation of target signature with woodland CB. Alternatively, carbon black pigment (CBP) has high absorption and low-reflection properties in IR spectrums. Thermal transparent binders such as polyethylene vinyl acetate copolymer and chlorinated polypropylene are suitable for camouflage treatment as the binder cannot change the reflection. Currently developed camouflage textiles can be detected from CB in the NIR spectrum. The military vehicle produces heat by the internal combustion engine and

terrestrial thermal emissions. The adaptation of emission between OB needs to be maintained for the concealment of the target signature. Temperature is a cause for the contrasting between the target signature and CB. Thermal insulation can be used for camouflage textiles when the surface temperature difference from the environment is more than 10°C. The application of thermal insulation materials is an option for secure protection and structuring UV–Vis–NIR camouflage textiles such as vehicle nets. Such fabric also protects against radar spectrums (3 to 3000 GHz) (M. A. Hossain, 2021c; Hossain, 2023aq; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2020; Pusch et al., 1985).

Camouflage textile materials in the IR range are made from synthetic fiber having ‘chlorophyll’ like reflectance characteristics in IR range such as polyamide and polyester (Horst & Guido, 2003). High reflection in the multidimensional direction to the viewing angle depicts the concealment of the target location. The high-reflection light theory is applied to camouflage for submarine concealment as marine

Fig. 10 Exponential relationship of woodland materials for natural plant-based natural dyes (NPND) for camouflage coloration and comparison with Cr oxide-coated textiles from 400 to 700 nm (a, b, c, d) and samples of Cr oxide-coated textiles against woodland materials and woodland background (e, f, g)

camouflage. Reflective metallic coatings of aluminum copper or zinc on the base layer achieve high reflectivity in the entire IR spectrums, but the technology has limited applications of camouflage textiles for concealment in UV–Vis–IR spectrums against multi-dimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. The protection against radar detection is achieved with coated materials for effectively reflecting radar radiation in all directions (Li et al., 2020) (Barbier et al., 2002; Gancheryonok & Lavrinenko, 2002; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a).

UV-Vis-NIR camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral cameras against defence surveillance

Hyperspectral camouflage means the protection of the target signature from surrounding CB in terms of hiding hyperspectral surveillance in UV–Vis–NIR spectrums. Chromatic blending of objects (camouflage textiles) with CB environment is the first attribute of hyperspectral camouflage textiles. Camouflage depends on the shape, size, hue, color contrast and mobility of the target object with CB. Differences in ATR,

Fig. 11 Exponential of Vis-IR photonic signal versus design of camouflage materials for simultaneous spectrum probe

scattering, diffraction and polarization of light between target OB identify the detectability or adaptability of target object against CBs-DGTWSICB. Hyperspectral, thermal, NIR, multispectral and anti-radar camouflaging are the critical challenge for the technological matching versus survivability of defence professionals. UV and NIR sensors of the hyperspectral camera have created a great challenge of hyperspectral camouflage. Recent augmentation of camouflage textiles only covers Vis ranges camouflage although there is a limitation of concealment in multidimensional CB environments in terms of lacking the right materials, methodologies, camouflage technologies and standardization. Recently developed camouflage textiles cannot fulfill the protection of UV-IR ranges surveillance technology in the vein of hyperspectral cameras or digital cameras. Colorant manufacturers are also struggling with camouflage dyes, but the right formulation is still a challenging fact. NIR reflectance dyes or pigment coating, aluminum-coated glass thermally bonded into non-woven, glass fabric and nonwoven fabric combination can be comprised in terms of photochromic (light), and thermochromic (heat) mechanism of camouflage textiles for augmentation of NIR camouflage. The simultaneous camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-NIR ranges are also a critical challenge to the research community, and the technology needs to coalesce through the optical mechanism of OB and suitable material design for camouflage textile coloration (Alka & Priyanka, 2017; A. Hossain, 2021b; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Li et al., 2020; Shami et al., 2017). In Figs. 7, 8, 9, and 11, the reflection coefficients and exponential trends of multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB in UV-Vis-NIR have been remarkably noted and hypothetically categorized in Table 1. This concept can be hypothetically

implemented for the design of camouflage materials in UV-Vis-NIR spectrums.

Advancement phase 5, material design for camouflage textile coloration against CBs-DGTWSICB under UV-Vis-IR spectrums

Optical principle of camouflage pigmentation for Vis-IR range concealment

Simultaneous applicable Vis-IR camouflage technology is proposed based on the metal-based structure of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Ag}/\text{ZnS}/\text{Ag}$ (Dong et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020). For simultaneous pigmentation in Vis-IR, the pigment should have simultaneous transparency in Vis-IR ranges. Vis camouflage textiles can be designed with a dark color or minimum gloss pigmentation, such as CBP and perylene black as the selective absorber. Metal oxide increases the concealment in the NIR and thermal IR ranges. Metal oxide absorbs in the NIR range, and these are transparent in the thermal IR range. Metal oxides (CeO_2 , TiO_2 , MgO and ZnO) show high reflection in simultaneous Vis-IR spectrums. The reflection variations between Vis and IR are nearest to 5%. As a hypothetical example, Fig. 12 depicts the exponential relationship of ZnO pigment in Vis-NIR spectrums. Reviewed data information is cited in Table S1 (q). Metal flakes, such as aluminium, reflect strongly in both the Vis and IR spectrums. Red iron oxide and titanium dioxide have a minimum scattering effect on light without altering the reflectance shape. Particles of 1 mm of red iron and titanium dioxide scatter NIR radiation at 2.3 mm. The refractive index of titanium dioxide and chromium oxide is 2.81 and 1.90, and their scattering powers (square meters) are 1.90 and 1.28, respectively. Titanium dioxide (mean particle size 10 μm) reflects between 800 and 2300 nm, and

Fig. 12 Exponential spectra of ZnO pigment in Vis–NIR spectrums from 400 to 2200 nm

comparatively less reflection is noted at 400–800 nm. Such compounds have atomic mobility and the light-striking capability of a target signature at a very high incident angle. There is a possibility of electron trapping between the target signature and CB, which mechanism may generate minor energy for the photonic signal to the remote sensing device. Hence, the light is also expected to scatter very quickly in the surrounding area of CB. The photonic signal of metal oxides to the spectral sensor cannot capture enough photons to generate an appropriate imaging signal of the target signature against CB. The high-reflection spectral signal may defend the genuine pixel formation of the target signature on the imaging sensor. Therefore, the target signature may be confused or concealed by the modern remote sensing mechanism of the target detector (Fang et al., 2013; Groning, 2002; Lummerstorfer & Hoffmann, 2004; Wake & Brady, 1993).

Commercial pigments are available such as color index (CI) pigment green 17, 26 and 50; CI pigment brown 29 and 35, pigment blue 28 and 36, pigment black 12 and white pigment base are also available such as white pigment titanium dioxide or zinc white, calcium carbonate, barium sulphate, alumina, silica, clay and aluminum powder; metal oxides such as zirconium oxide and thorium oxide; metallic pigment such as aluminum and mica flakes; high refractive index pigments such as titanium dioxide, chromium oxide, zinc sulphide, zinc oxide, aluminium, gold, silver and copper. A combination of different IR-reflective pigments may enhance the total reflection of the coated

surface. Particle size can be selected from 0.35 to 0.55 microns (Ashwini & Malshe, 2008; Cui, 2011). Chromium oxide, iron oxide and carbozel violet pigments are referred to as camouflage pigments due to their reflectance properties both in Vis and NIR (Muzaffer & Yavuz, 2010). A deep-color camouflaging formulation is implemented on aircraft when the CB is considered as dark sea. Colors are formulated by titanium dioxide, organic perylene black and red, blue and yellow oxides based on polyurethane (PU) resin (hexamethylene diisocyanate). Microfine silica is also used as gloss reducing agent. A grey color formulation is used for countershaded aircraft (Wake, 1993). IR pigments (chrome oxide green, carbon black) have great advantages for simultaneous camouflage in Vis–NIR. The pigmentation technique allows color matching with specific CB in Vis, and the reflection principle allows to blending of the target signature with CB color in the NIR range (Muzaffer & Yavuz, 2010). Synthetic coloration with low-reflection materials such as CBP declines the detectability in the Vis range, and there is scope for NIR range experimentation (Rudolf, 1978). CBP is a traditional colorant. It absorbs UV–Vis–NIR wavelengths of light. The particle size denotes the physical properties of the pigmentation, such as color strength, stability and light scattering ability. Even a small amount of IR-absorbing material in total weight can significantly reduce IR reflectivity. The reflection of objects can be tested using a UV–Vis–NIR spectrophotometer in the optical mechanism of ATR (Cui, 2011; Jose et al., 2019).

Optical engineering of synthetic pigmentation for simultaneous camouflage in Vis–NIR against woodland CB

A synthetic pigmented surface has the properties of NIR reflection. Pigments are synthesized by the mixtures of metal hydroxide, nitrates, acetates and oxides at very high temperature ranges over 1000°C. Metal and oxygen ions are oriented in a stable crystal structure; the process is called 'calcination'. IR reflective coating is highly used for building construction; it can also minimize the surface heating of textile substances. IR-reflective pigments are suitable for NIR camouflage textiles to reduce the heating effect on color change. The remaining high percentage of mobile electrons depicts high reflection on the surface. The functional properties of calcinated pigments have a dual action of absorption and reflection. The pigment absorbs light in the visible region and is appropriate for Vis camouflage. The pigmentation technology of dual camouflaging seems more accurate for the concealment of Vis–NIR camera surveillance. For example, the 'chlorophyll' of green plants reflects IR light. The green plant of woodland CB contains 'chlorophyll', and it has organic pigment for IR reflection. 'Chlorophyll' is also termed a natural IR reflective material, applicable for woodland camouflage textiles. Practically, a tree background is cooler than the surrounding background in a hot summer (Ashwini & Malshe, 2008; Cui, 2011).

Optical engineering of thermal insulation for camouflage formulation

Planck's law states that the IR range is mostly related to thermal radiation. Hence, IR camouflage textiles need a combination of thermal insulation materials. Silica aerogel has thermal insulation properties which can reduce the surface temperature of camouflage textiles. Phase change materials (PCMs) have found limited applications for camouflage textiles. For consideration of concealment, germanium is a high IR reflective material for target confusing versus camouflaging response. A thermal insulation-reflection combination of silica aerogel and germanium is proposed for NIR range camouflage textiles for aircraft and missile target protection. High-temperature aircraft nozzles and high-temperature naval ship funnels are also challenging for the design of sky camouflage and marine camouflage. The real protection of fighting aircraft and marine ships is still challenging (Huanzheng et al., 2020). A combination of thermal insulation and high reflective coating has been commented to be more effective for defence target concealment (Anthony, 2005). NIR anti-reflection coating is formulated by the

combination of silicon and germanium (Cox & Hass, 1958). The concept of technology in NIR range camouflage textiles has been still limited. There is a feasibility of NIR range camouflage incorporating a combination of PCMs such as $\text{Ge}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_5$ (Qu et al., 2018) and VO_2 . The combination has the phenomenon of phase transition and reflection changing for NIR camouflaging (Sayan et al., 2018). Surface reflection of camouflage textiles depends on treatment with suitable materials. The mechanism defines the reflection and transmittance of OB as referred by the theory of 'Augustin-Jean Fresnel'. Low-reflection coatings and fabrication design are another way of camouflage principle (Raut et al., 2011). IR absorbing CBP can be applied for enhancement of IR absorption.

Stealth is the act or characteristics that confuse the detection by chromatic replacement and/or shape. The animal has the camouflaging techniques of stealth skin (Hossain, 2023bj, 2023bk; Shim et al., 2022). Low emissivity denotes the IR shielding property of stealth skin (Li et al. 2022). The simultaneous development of smart textiles and camouflaging property can be developed by microfabrication and stealth skin. Surface dyeing and pigmentation, embedded additives, chromic materials, low emissivity coatings and fibers, PCMs, and shape memory materials are the existing technologies in smart camouflage textiles (Degenstein et al., 2021). Metasurface is also an optical engineering that can create negative refraction (Klar et al., 2006). Metasurface can be used to reduce optical scattering for camouflage (Joy et al., 2021; Klar et al., 2006).

Optical engineering of camouflage coloration with nanomaterials

TiO_2 , ZnO and Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles were applied for IR protection. Camouflaging nanobeads can be used with textile dyes for deceiving formulations of camouflage coloration. There is advanced suitability of nanomaterials for camouflage clothing. Nanomaterials can enhance defence textile properties such as fabric softness, durability, breathability, water repellency, fire retardancy, antimicrobial, UV protection and shrink-proof (Sawhney et al., 2008). Nano titanium dioxide increases surface reflection (Reza et al., 2018). Cotton-nylon blended fabrics are printed using a mixture of pigments and carbon black nanoparticles for camouflage coloration. Shading of brown, olive green and khaki was employed in the desert uniform. The printing formulation remarked a significant decline in limited ranges of NIR reflectance (Mehrizi et al., 2012; Mehrizi et al., 2015). The structure of camouflage coloration is also formulated by the core (chromophore materials)

and sheath (polymer) processes (Sudhakar et al., 2008). A polyvinylidene fluoride resin can be used as a transparent binder (Wake & Brady, 1993).

Optical engineering of camouflage coloration with thermochromic dyes

The thermochromic colorant can be blended with pigment to match the CB environment. Thermoplastic PU and graphite are mixed and coated for thermochromic coloration. Thermochromism and camouflage coloration can be tested by CIE red, green, blue, L^* , a^* and b^* . These values and imaging properties can be recorded before and after heating for assessment of infrared (IR) camouflaging against selected CB (Karpagam et al., 2016; Samolov et al., 2021). Liquid crystal is also a unique material for temperature-responsive fabrication. Chiral nematic liquid crystal changes its color in the presence of thermal, electrical and optical stimuli. This phenomenon is responsible for changing the refractive index or pitch. Formulation of indolyfulgide chiral dopants shows color stability adjustment. The color stability of chiral nematic liquid crystal has been observed for smart applications of camouflage textiles (M. A. Hossain, 2021a; Timothy J et al., 2012). The thermochromic dye 'crystal violate lactone' was used as core material, and silica was used as shell material. The thermochromic effects and color reversibility were observed at wavelength 610 nm under consideration of shifting color strength and K/S value from 12 to 2 (Wan et al., 2017). Hence, thermochromic colorants may have a feasibility for camouflaging against selected CB.

Optical engineering of camouflage coloration with synthetic dyes

Cotton, polyester, nylon and cotton-polyester blends are general applications of camouflage textiles (Ministry of Defence). Nomex and Kevlar are suitable for high-performance applications of camouflage textiles. Spun-bonded nonwoven fabric is experimented with random orientation of metal fibril on the fabric surface to obtain the expected camouflage formulation. Filling hollow fibers with liquid dyes and solid pigment is a proposed technique for adaptive camouflage textiles (Adanur & Tewari, 1997). Common methods of fabricating camouflage textiles are dyeing, coating and printing (Uranus et al., 2014). Coating and printing are suitable techniques for man-made or natural fiber-based camouflage textiles (Burkinshaw et al., 1996; Rudolf, 1978). Printing is a method of camouflage patterning. Camouflage patterns on the fabric are produced using low-reflectance dyes having thiazine at a relatively long wavelengths greater than 900 nm (Dale R, 2015). The reflectance profile of woodland

camouflage textiles is experimented by different disperse dyes, such as CI disperse black, CI disperse yellow 23, CI disperse blue 14 and disperse blue 56. The reflectance of camouflage-treated objects and greenish leaves background was compared with CIE L^* , a^* , b^* , c^* and h for chromatic variation. The process interprets a minimum level of woodland camouflaging; it has demanded a further level of experimentation. CI disperse blue 56 shows the effect of green leaves camouflaging on polyester fabric (Hui & Jianchun, 2007). Vat blue 13 dye has also green camouflaging properties in Vis and limited NIR regions (Goudarzi et al., 2013; Vitalija et al., 2008; Zhang & Zhang, 2008). Vat dyes have low IR reflectance and good fastness properties, making them suitable for camouflage applications on cotton textiles. Tetraaryldiamine dyes absorb in IR (Ramsey et al., 2019).

Advancement phase 6, method design for CDRI measurement of target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB under UV-Vis-IR spectrums Spectrometry and colorimetry versus CDRI assessment

In general, wavelengths more than 700 nm are considered as IR range. The visible spectrum covers wavelengths from 400 to 700 nm. The wavelengths 200 to 400 nm are depicted as the UV spectrum. Both UV and IR rays are invisible to humans due to a lack of receptors. Ray directions are a matter of light reflection, such as specular reflection and diffuse reflection. Single outgoing reflection is termed specular reflection, and multiple-angle reflection is termed diffuse reflection. A color measurement spectrophotometer can be used to measure the reflectance, transmittance or absorbance of target OB at different wavelengths. A specular included method is used for total reflection, and a specular excluded method is used for diffuse reflectance of OB substances. The color variation of specular included and specular excluded is verified by ceramic tiles of 12 standard reference colors (white, pale grey, middle grey, deep grey, orange, deep pink, black, red, bright yellow, green, cyan and deep blue) for colorimetry and spectrometry. This method is used by the British ceramics research association (BCRA). Hence, the mechanism of visual assessment of camouflage is more critical than the pass/fail decision of solid colors. CIE color difference is an established method of color deviation between OB, where luminance, hue and chroma are the contrast features of chromatic adaptation for variations of target OB. The chromatic adaptation of desert sand, urban grey and foliage green is experimented by CIE color parameters; the method cannot cover multidimensional angles (Gang, 2012). CIE colorimetry is the mechanism of color

matching and predicting the color difference between two stimuli for the identification of physical color. The technique has limitations for actual color appearance between OB due to structural variation of the object (camouflage textiles) and CB. Chromatic properties of camouflage-formulated textiles, camouflage materials and DGTWSICB materials are mostly demonstrated by the CIE trichromatic hue of RGB and the CIE L*, a* and b* color coordinates. The UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer cannot measure color directly; it measures the physical attributes of materials concerning their ATR of light. A digital camera or hyperspectral camera can be used to measure the chromatic appearance of OB in a controlled optical environment of OB. A digital camera can be used for the color measurement of OB when highly textured and printed materials cannot be measured by color measurement spectrophotometer. The light reflected from OB is passed through the lens, and imaging is captured through two-dimensional sensors covered with RGB color filters (Kulapurath, 2018).

Hyperspectral versus CDRI assessment of target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB

Hyperspectral imaging is an improved and modified version of multispectral imaging used for target detection and defence surveillance in the UV-Vis-NIR ranges. Captured target signatures and CBs in a hyperspectral image are difficult to characterize in terms of identification and quantification of concealment. Generally, target object (camouflage textiles) analysis of hyperspectral concealment needs to generate a spectral database of multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. Interfering elements of CDRI are not the same for all CBs. These interferences need to be identified for all CBs for camouflage textiles. A standard

spectral database identifies the discrimination of OB by means of a spectrum probe. Spectral properties are controlled by scattering effects on OB. Treated camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-NIR are classified as supervised target detection of hyperspectral cameras due to having known and predicted properties on textile substances. The target signature can be analyzed in terms of known CB for the experimental process. Spectral angle, spectral distance and spectral information are the properties of spectral symmetry. To avoid interfering reflection of imaging, the specification of the target is very important for camouflage assessment of hyperspectral imaging. A simulation of spectral symmetry was conducted for typical signatures including CB materials such as black brush, creosote leaves, sagebrush, red soil and dry grass. The reflection of the interferer varies from CB to CB. The spectral properties of DGTWSICB materials are not the same. A real experimentation of hyperspectral camouflage textiles for spectral symmetry is required. Spectral symmetry and its analyses between target OB are existing techniques in prediction, simulation and planning stages only. Target signature versus CBs-DGTWSICB measurement of spectral similarity and dissimilarity of hyperspectral imaging is still challenging in optical engineering and the unknown journey of camouflage researchers (Chang, 2003; A. Hossain, 2021b; Kent Andersson, 2014).

Mechanism of CDRI measurement for target signature against CBs-DGTWSICB

Pixel is another approach of camouflage signature evaluation for image segmentation and comparison of hyperspectral imaging between OB. The task is very challenging due to the lack of standardization for the comparison of hyperspectral imaging (Chang, 2003).

Fig. 13 Flow chart for the principle of camouflage assessment

Spectral imaging is a practicable technology for CDRI of target signature against CB. The signal of spectral imaging can provide strong performance for analyses of the optical properties of the target object (camouflage textiles) and CB (X. Briottet et al., 2006). Spectral discrimination has been remarked as a potential issue for day or night surveillance of military targets. The performance of CDRI is achievable in terms of high band-to-band multispectral and hyperspectral sensors (Michael T et al.). Electromagnetic optics, radiometry, photometry and human psychometrics are the technical areas for the assessment of CDRI. It is necessary to develop an accurate process of concealment measurement for supporting camouflage assessment. As summarized in Fig. 13, camouflage measurement on CB has been concerned with presumption, simulation, analysis and laboratory trialing, field experimentation and structural judgment. Simulation and prediction represent the decision based on the predetermined processes. Analysis and laboratory experiments include quantitative and partial measurements for camouflage assessment. Field experimentation and structural judgment are the process of the real game of concealment in multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB (Farrar, 1878; Stephen, 2015).

Image processing techniques for CDRI measurement against CBs-DGTWSICB

Every field experimentation for camouflage assessment is an expensive process. Natural illumination, target object, target CB and location of target OB are the real facts for every combat trialing of camouflage achievement (Peak et al.). Photographs of formulated textiles against CBs can be captured by digital camera or hyperspectral camera at a specified angle and illumination for comparison between the object (textile substances) and its surrounding CB. Lens changing of digital camera is an option for capturing photographs in different spectrums of UV-Vis-IR. The post-image analyses are conducted by image processing software such as Adobe Photoshop, ImageJ and environment for visualizing images. Digital images can be modified into CIE-RGB color space to CIE L^* , a^* and b^* color space under a black-white grey scale of chromatic hue. CIE L^* , a^* and b^* color space is defined between -127 and $+127$ for each axis of three-dimensional color space. Eight bits are suitable to interpret the color space. Color threshold is a chromatic and achromatic identification process functioned in ImageJ. This software covers CIE red, green, blue, L^* , a^* and b^* color coordinates in a black-white grey scale. The chromatic variation is a process applied for the identification of camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. For

example, fractal design (a typical percentage of CB is matched with textile objects rather than matching the whole object with the background) is a common practice of defence professionals for forest and desert camouflage in the single background only. Recent research on camouflage textiles is mostly limited to the Vis range and chromatic assessment covers mostly photographic systems rather than establishing quantitative systems. Hyperspectral camouflage textiles have a great limitation for the right materials on textile substances for hyperspectral concealment and their quantitative and photographic/partial assessment process for camouflage textile performance. Hyperspectral images in multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB needs to generate an accurate view in specific lighting, angle and resolution for the detection of camouflage properties on textile substances (Mehrizi et al., 2012; Ramli et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2021). Color and intensity features of an image can signify the camouflage assessment and camouflage detection. Texture analysis with image processing is a very effective way of camouflage assessment for classification, segmentation and CDRI. Less intensity of an image depicts the appearance of dark camouflage and brighter intensity of an image creates the appearance of light camouflage (A. Hossain, 2021a; Hossain, 2009; Sujit et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2021).

Advancement phase 7, significant advancement of camouflage textiles against modern defence surveillance in UV-Vis-NIR spectrums

Camouflage textiles do not mean camouflage clothing only. There are enormous concepts of applications of textile-based camouflage by means of spectrum probe in UV-Vis-NIR such as temporary combat residence, vehicle and location hiding, radar protection, missile protection, parachute protection, nuclear weapon and ballistic protection. Camouflage textiles for multidimensional single CB, simultaneous CB and adaptive CB need to be well established for defence protection. Recent research on camouflage textiles is only intended for 'CB color matching' in terms of chromatic and patterning, but 'color matching theory' is only applicable to the visible range while camouflage engineering is also required in UV-NIR ranges. The reflection angle of the target signature changes the color appearance of the human observer or digital camera or hyperspectral camera. Surrounding environment colors of CB are not limited to any single CB. CB colors change with location, season, foggy weather, sunny weather, rainy weather and bushfire of woodland. Currently developed camouflage requirement concentrates on limited ranges of spectrum probes and a minimum number of CB environments. Target objects are still detectable by

the reflection of CB materials. Military camouflage textiles are already developed in the Vis range, and there is a limitation of camouflage textiles in UV-NIR against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB. Furthermore, research on UV-Vis-NIR range camouflage textiles and the suitability of the right camouflage materials for concealment are limited in published literature. High-performance camouflage textiles can be achieved by proper implementation of deceiving materials on textile substances. Conventional textile coloration processes (coating, dyeing or printing) can be applied for the treatment of textile substances with advanced formulation of camouflage textiles. Existing camouflage textiles are not suitable for simultaneous camouflaging in UV-Vis-NIR ranges. There is a need for common textiles for camouflage in UV-Vis-NIR ranges. Temperature changing versus chromatic replacement or thermal changing versus chromatic stabilization created a demanding source of research and development in camouflage textiles for the protection of defence professionals. The establishment of proposed technological advancement and the right formulation of deceiving materials may generate an output of high-performance camouflage textiles in versatile

single CB environments, adaptive camouflage for multi-dimensional CB environments, UV-Vis-IR camouflage, hyperspectral camera and radar protective camouflage for concealment of defence target signature.

Limitation of camouflage research, review and related findings

This review of camouflage textiles shows a limited number of research and publications in the specific area of high-performance camouflage textiles, but most research demonstrates prototype experimentation in a limited condition of individual research deficient with a deeper concept of advanced analysis in UV-Vis-IR illumination against multidimensional CB material-DGTWSICB, methodology and materials for camouflage formulation and right spectrometry for CDRI. Some patents have been published with lacking a concrete credential of material, methods and real testing processes of camouflage formulation. The research and innovation in military camouflage might be a hidden activity of military scientist groups for keeping self-implementation of newly generated technology for any specific group and/or any country.

Fig. 14 Optical principle of concealment and detection (C & D) between observer (a, b, c, d) and target signature (a1, b1, c1, d1)

Therefore, materials, methodologies and real testing methods of camouflage textiles are not being widely published. This review may opine a framework of right camouflage materials, methods and target illumination for designing advanced camouflage textiles in terms of digital and hyperspectral imaging under UV–Vis–IR surveillance.

Advancement phase 8, the principle of optical approach for camouflage textile coloration for concealment against digital camera imaging/ hyperspectral imaging in UV–Vis–IR spectrums

Camouflage coloration denotes altering the reflection of the textile surface by using technical coloration such as coating, dyeing and printing. Deceiving materials on textile substances are mainly termed as pigments, nanoparticles, dyes, and eco-friendly sources of natural materials. Figure 14a, a1 shows the structural similarity of expected camouflage materials between OB when the target signature is depicted as zero reflection against CB, the human observer or digital camera or hyperspectral camera will not obtain a clear image of the real target for detection. Textile materials can be directly treated with CB source of natural materials such as NPND and NSSD for concealment against woodland, desertland, rockland, concreteland or urban and water or marine CBs (A. Hossain, 2020; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022c; Hossain, 2023ck; M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018). In Fig. 14b, b1; high-light absorbency materials have been classified as low-reflection materials. The reflection of the target object will not be perceived as a low reflection of the object material. Therefore, minimum reflection of object materials has the feasibility of camouflage coloration due to negligible response of photonic signal to remote sensing devices such as digital imaging or hyperspectral imaging. In Fig. 14c, c1; similarly, the exact reflection of the target signature will not be perceived by the human observer or digital camera or hyperspectral camera for high-reflection materials. The photonic signal will be scattered in the multidimensional direction without reaching the actual signal to the sensor of a surveillance camera. Textile materials can be treated based on the functional mechanism of high-reflection materials such as selected nanoparticles, germanium, aluminium, and titanium dioxide based on selected CB. In Figs. 14d, d1; the combination of reflection of changing materials has the capability of altering reflection to the imaging devices. In this optical principle, light will be reflected at different angles which can be twisted by the reflection mechanism and

misperception of the image will be detected to signify the target signature against CBs–DGTWSICB. Typical angles are defined and remarked by showing arrow marks. For every UV–Vis–NIR surveillance, camera sensors of digital camera or hyperspectral camera generate imaging from photon signal of target signature and CB materials. Reflection and spectral signals of the target signature (camouflage textiles) may alter photon signals for deceiving the target signature against CB. In the thermochromic principle, the chromatic replacement will occur in a specific temperature range; the same camouflage textile is possible to implement in different CB environments in terms of chromatic matching in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. Thermal insulation is the opposite principle of the chromatic phenomenon. Color will not change in a specific temperature range; the same camouflage textile has the technical feasibility to use battlefield operations in different temperatures in terms of chromatic matching and UV–Vis–IR camouflaging (M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a).

Advancement phase 9, a hierarchical model for camouflage textile formulation and optical assessment for CDRI-target signature–DGTWSICB–UV–Vis–IR

Figure 15 shows the standardized process of UV–Vis–IR camouflage textile formulation and performance measurement steps, which are segmented into nine categories for CDRI assessment of target signature against CBs–DGTWSICB and its surrounding environment.

Segment 1: Target CB selection is a primary attempt for camouflage coloration. Single CB or simultaneous CB or adaptive CB can be selected for the target signature. DGTWSICBs are the common CB area for the technical formulation of camouflage textiles as per geographical combat—the province of the different countries (Kang et al., 2016).

Segment 2: The deceiving materials need to be selected for the concealment of specific CB environments. Reflection-changing materials, reflection-matching materials, thermochromic dyes, liquid crystal, crystal violet lactone, thermal insulation materials and CB source-based NPND–NSSD materials are selected as the main deceiving materials for UV–Vis–IR camouflage textiles in multidimensional CB environment–DGTWSICB. Deceiving materials can be encapsulated by a transparent polymeric binder. Thermochromic and thermal insulation effects on chromatic stability and its camouflaging performance can be tested under different temperature ranges (M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a; Tözüm et al., 2018).

Fig. 15 Flow chart of technical formulation for design of camouflage textiles against DGTWSICB and optical assessment for CDRI in UV-Vis-IR imaging

Segment 3: The suitability of deceiving materials treatment for camouflage textiles can be experimented by coating, dyeing and printing processes of textile coloration. These techniques can be modified by the combination of coloration processes to achieve camouflage in different CB environment-DGTWSICBs.

Segment 4: The concealment properties of camouflage-treated textiles against the selected materials of DGTWSICB can be identified in Vis and limited NIR ranges by color measurement spectrophotometer. Both the specular included and excluded methods can be used for the chromatic analysis of formulated textiles and combat materials. For illumination measurement of glossy materials, the specular included option is the most suitable for capturing the highest reflection in diffuse illumination. Furthermore, the structural properties of camouflage, chromatic compound identification and related chemometric analysis can be executed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared

spectroscopy (FTIR) and UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer for laboratory stage trialing (Aleksandra et al., 2019).

Segment 5: The evidence of target signature in UV-Vis-IR range surveillance can be implemented by a digital camera. The digital camera can reveal the target signature against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB (Garcia et al., 2013).

Segment 6: The captured photographs of the digital camera can be analyzed by image processing software (ImageJ) for confirmation of CDRI under CIE red, green, blue, L*, a* and b* chromatic hue of black-white grey scale. The OB image can be segmented by the color threshold method (A. Hossain, 2021a; Yang et al., 2021).

Segment 7: Quantitative color differences of OB can be judged by CIE L*, a*, b*, c* and h values. Achromatic features of target signature and CBs and their effects can also be identified for CDRI assessment. Hence, the chromatic and achromatic assessments of target signature versus DGTWSICB can be

experimented by photographic illumination in UV–Vis–IR (Garcia et al., 2013; A. Hossain, 2021a; M. A. Hossain, 2021c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Liu et al., 2008; Samolov et al., 2021).

Segment 8: Hyperspectral camera can be used for high-performance applications of camouflage assessment in UV–Vis–NIR ranges from 200 to 2500 nm (Lu et al., 2022; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2020; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2022).

Segment 9: Optical accuracy of spectral design for spectral symmetry, chromatic appearance and illumination properties can signify the CDRI of target signature against selected CB. The ATR properties of camouflage-treated textiles and CB materials can be experimented in UV–Vis–NIR ranges from 200 to 2500 nm (Ko et al., 2007; Lu et al., 2022; Mikkelsen & Selj, 2022). Target signature against DGTWSICB captured by hyperspectral camera can also be assessed by image processing software. Therefore, the chromatic aberration of multidimensional color and texture of the target signature and CBs can be assessed for CDRI.

Concluding remarks

ATR properties of the formulated textile surface, ATR properties of selected CB materials, chromatic appearance of digital or hyperspectral imaging, CIE trichromatic hue, structural features, sun radiation related to weather conditions and humidity, illumination angle, imaging sensors of digital camera, or hyperspectral camera and electromagnetic spectrums in UV–Vis–IR are the key principle for every CDRI evaluation of target signature against dry leaves, green leaves and tree bark-woodland combat background; water-marine combat background; sand-desertland combat background; stone-stoneland combat background; snow-snowland combat background; sky combat background; ice-iceland combat background; and concrete-concreteland combat background (DGTWSICB) and its surrounding combat environments. Imaging signals of CDRI mostly depend on electron energy and photonic signal of target signature in UV–Vis–IR illumination. Camouflage textiles can be detected by human eyes (Vis) or instrumental investigations such as spectroscopy, microscopy, digital cameras and hyperspectral cameras. The reflectance profile of a target signature (camouflage textiles) can be matched with the reflectance profile of CB in the vein of chromatic, achromatic and spectral illumination. For chromatic matching between target objects and CBs, the selection of correct deceiving materials is the first task for camouflage textile formulation. Hence, appropriate treatment of camouflage materials on textile substances may signify the concealment of the target signature in multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB under

UV–Vis–IR illumination. Camouflage materials can be treated on textile substances by the conventional technology of dyeing-coating-printing-padding. The chromatic standardization of CB materials in the laboratory stage has been opined for chromatic assessment of CB versus camouflage-treated textiles. The core materials of CB and camouflage-formulated textiles can be considered for CDRI assessment in the laboratory stage as real CB materials have variations due to known and unknown interference in CB environments. These unknown parameters of CBs can be controlled sequentially if textile-treated materials can be concealed or matched against CB materials under selected illumination in UV–Vis–IR spectrums, and it may have the core achievement for the design of camouflage textiles. Therefore, the target signature can be concealed under the interference of the CB environment and natural illumination in field trialing. Reflecting the color of the target signature and CB creates the imaging signal rather than the absorbed color. White CB of the natural environment reflects the entire wavelength of visible light. Other CB absorbs light at specific wavelengths. Such as the green leaves background of woodland CB reflects green color and absorbs another color; the snow background of snowland CB reflects in full spectrum of visible wavelength. Electron energy of camouflage materials of target signature can replace the wavelength and imaging signal in digital and hyperspectral imaging. Textile substances can be treated with zero reflection materials, natural materials, CB source-based natural materials such as NPND and NSSD, minimum or maximum reflection materials, multi-reflection materials for replacement or matching of electron energy against CBs and/or confusing the target signature. The electron energy of target signature generates the energy of the photon signal to be detected by imaging sensors and surveillance cameras. Therefore, the spectral signal of zero-reflection or high-reflection materials may create simultaneous camouflaging in UV–Vis–IR spectrums. A hyperspectral camera can be used for chromatic and spectral observation of CDRI using a wide proportion of electromagnetic spectrums in UV–Vis–NIR ranges. The concealment of the latest surveillance in UV–Vis–NIR illumination can be premeditated by altering or symmetrization of surface reflection of the target object with CB. The distance between the camera and the target signature creates a variation of the photon signal. The position of the target object vibrates the velocity of electron energy and photonic signal to the imaging sensor. Reflection of the target object, conditions of the CB environment, single CB or simultaneous CBs, and the right selection of deceiving materials

Table 2 Camouflage materials design, method design and testing formulations against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB

Expected outcome-01: Design of woodland camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
Total Trials (Ts)	Formulations	Materials	Methods	Lab/Field Testing
T-01	Formulation-01	Chromium oxide	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-02	Formulation-02	Aluminium nanoparticle		
T-03	Formulation-03	Chromium oxide + Aluminium nanoparticle		
T-04	Formulation-04	Natural materials of woodland, NPND		
T-05	Formulation-05	Chromium oxide + CBP		
T-06	Formulation-06	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
Expected outcome-02: Design of desert camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-07	Formulation-01	Mica powder	Camouflage bead formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-08	Formulation-02	Titanium dioxide + Aluminium nanoparticle		
T-09	Formulation-03	Mica powder + Aluminium nanoparticle		
T-10	Formulation-04	Natural materials of desertland, NSSD		
T-11	Formulation-05	Selected acid Dyes		
T-12	Formulation-06	Mica powder + CBP		
Expected outcome-03: Design of water/marine camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-13	Formulation-01	Titanium dioxide	Deceiving bead formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-14	Formulation-02	Germanium nanoparticle		
T-15	Formulation-03	Titanium dioxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-16	Formulation-04	Titanium dioxide + CBP		
T-17	Formulation-05	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-18	Formulation-06	CBP + Germanium nano particle		
Expected outcome-04: Design of snowland/sky camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-19	Formulation-01	Lead oxide	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-20	Formulation-02	Titanium dioxide		
T-21	Formulation-03	Germanium nanoparticle		
T-22	Formulation-04	Lead oxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-23	Formulation-05	Titanium dioxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-24	Formulation-06	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-25	Formulation-07	Titanium dioxide + CBP		

Table 2 (continued)

Expected outcome-05: Design of iceland camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-26	Formulation-01	Zinc oxide	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-27	Formulation-02	Titanium dioxide		
T-28	Formulation-03	Germanium nanoparticle		
T-29	Formulation-04	Zinc oxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-30	Formulation-05	Titanium dioxide + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-31	Formulation-06	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-32	Formulation-07	Titanium dioxide + CBP		
Expected outcome-06: Design of stoneland/concreteland/urban camouflage textiles/simultaneous background camouflage for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-33	Formulation-01	Natural materials of stoneland	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer, UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, SEM, FTIRs, Digital camera, Hyperspectral camera, Image processing software
T-34	Formulation-02	Germanium nanoparticle		
T-35	Formulation-03	Pumic powder + Germanium nanoparticle		
T-36	Formulation-04	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-37	Formulation-05	Pumic powder + CBP		
Expected Outcome-07: Design of temperature adaptive camouflage textiles for concealment in UV-Vis-IR spectrums				
T-38	Formulation-01	Thermochromic leuco dyes + liquid crystal	Deceiving beads formation by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on PA 6,6 fabric/other selected fabrics	Color measurement Spectrophotometer UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer SEM, FTIRs Digital camera Hyperspectral camera Image processing software
T-39	Formulation-02	Thermochromic leuco dyes + PCM		
T-40	Formulation-03	Thermochromic leuco dyes + PCM + Liquid crystal		
T-41	Formulation-04	Selected synthetic dyes and its technical formulation		
T-42	Formulation-05	Thermochromic leuco dyes + PCM + Liquid crystal + Germanium		

are the matter of altering the electron state or photon signal for the accuracy of concealment under UV-Vis-IR spectrums. Hence, the advancement of camouflage textile technology can be implemented for concealment of modern defence surveillance in UV-Vis-IR spectrums against multidimensional CBs-DGTWS-ICB. Furthermore, the principle of material design versus optical engineering has outermost applications of camouflage weapon design against hyperspectral or digital camera surveillance in UV-Vis-NIR spectrums. Camouflage product developers need to consider

spectral signals for every high-performance concealment as upcoming surveillance is gradually vibrating from more sophisticated to sophisticated. Table 2, in terms of a review of the optical hypothesis, the author coalesced '42 possible formulations' for advanced design of camouflage textiles/CDRI trialing against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB in UV-Vis-IR illumination and expected outcomes (1-7) have been tabulated. In general, camouflage bead formation is proposed by microencapsulation with PU binder and coating/dyeing/printing/padding on polyamide 6,6 (PA

Table 3 A summary of research output and analysis of the sole author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University for camouflage materials design, optical design, method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering and camouflage textiles against multidimensional CBs-DGTWSICB since 2019-2020

Name of Titles	Invention in camouflage analysis
<p>➤ Concealment, Detection, Recognition, and Identification of Target Signature on Water Background under Natural Illumination. <i>International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations</i>, 10(117), 1–11, Article 1,011,721–01. http://www.ijsei.com/papers/ijsei-1011721-01.pdf; https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8242827; https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10885.32487</p>	<p>➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, and camouflage assessment in general ➤ Color analysis for camouflage engineering, color engineering, and camouflage assessment in general ➤ Environmental facts and weather for CDRI, camouflage engineering, color engineering, and camouflage assessment in general</p>
<p>➤ Spectral simulation and method design of camouflage textiles for concealment of hyperspectral imaging in UV–Vis-IR against multidimensional combat background. <i>The Journal of the Textile Institute</i>, 1–12. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2022.2027074</p>	<p>➤ Optical design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage assessment ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage assessment</p>
<p>➤ Adaptive Camouflage Textiles with Thermochromic Colorant and Liquid Crystal for Multidimensional Combat Background, a Technical Approach for Advancement in Defence Protection. <i>American Journal of Materials Engineering and Technology</i>, 9(1), 31–47. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.12691/materials-9-1-3</p>	<p>➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage assessment ➤ Thermochromic material design for CDRI camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage textiles, and camouflage assessment ➤ A concept of adaptive camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Evaluation of Camouflage Coloration of Polyamide-6,6 Fabric by Comparing Simultaneous Spectrum in Visible and Near-Infrared Region for Defense Applications. In A. K. Samanta (Ed.), <i>Colorimetry</i> (pp. 1–22). IntechOpen. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.95699</p>	<p>➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Carbon black coated camouflage textiles in terms of low reflection textiles</p>
<p>➤ Camouflage Assessment of Aluminium Coated Textiles for Woodland and Desertland Combat Background in Visible and Infrared Spectrum under UV–Vis-IR Background Illumination. <i>Defence Science Journal</i>, 72(3), 359–370. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.14429/dsj.72.17731</p>	<p>➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Aluminium coated desertland camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Ecofriendly Camouflage Textiles with Natural Sand-based Silicon Dioxide against Simultaneous Combat Background of Woodland, Desertland, Rockland, Concreteland and Water/Marine. <i>Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square</i> https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2359705/v1</p>	<p>➤ Natural material and method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Silicon Dioxide coated desertland camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Simulation of chromatic and achromatic assessments for camouflage textiles and combat background. <i>Journal of Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology</i>, 1–16. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/15485129211067759</p>	<p>➤ Key optical parameters for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ A Practical Guideline of Few Standardized Ready Made Shades of Natural Dyed Textiles. In A. K. Samanta & N. S. Awwad (Eds.), <i>Chemistry and Technology of Natural and Synthetic Dyes and Pigments</i> (pp. 151–170). IntechOpen. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.92360</p>	<p>➤ Natural material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. <i>Scientific Reports</i>. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2</p>	<p>➤ Optical design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ A concept of natural plant based natural dyes (NPND) coated woodland camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. <i>MRS Communications</i> https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3</p>	<p>➤ Optical design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles for protection of defense target signature in UV–Visible–IR spectrum opposing of hyperspectral and digital imaging. <i>Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square</i> 1–18. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2298847/v1</p>	<p>➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Cr oxide coated woodland camouflage textiles</p>
<p>➤ Coloration of polyamide-6,6 fabric with carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles of simultaneous spectrum probe in visible and near infrared. <i>Advance Research in Textile Engineering, Austin Publishing Group</i>. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36504.98560; https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297554</p>	<p>➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Carbon black nano particle for camouflage textiles in terms of low reflection textiles</p>

Table 3 (continued)

Name of Titles	Invention in camouflage analysis
➤ Advancement in UV–Vis–IR camouflage Textiles for concealment of defense surveillance against multidimensional combat background. <i>Preprint (Version 2) available at Preprint.Org; Preprint (Version 1) available at Research Square.</i> https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2549022/v1 ; https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648 ; https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117436	➤ Optical theory for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Material design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles ➤ Method design for camouflage engineering, color engineering, camouflage assessment, and camouflage textiles
➤ Advancement in UV–Visible–IR Camouflage Textiles and Camouflage Physics. In <i>Scholarly Community Encyclopedia</i> . https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/history/show/112736	➤ Optical theory for camouflage engineering

6,6) and/or other selected fabric required by defence professionals for combat action of camouflaging.

The exact brightness or dullness of materials depends on atomic number in general. The atomic number relates to the optical engineering of electrons (Eby et al., 2010). The responses of electron energy relate to the responses of photons. The photonic response generates UV–Vis–IR imaging of the surveillance mechanism in the defence platform. The responses of photons cause the deviation between target objects and combat backgrounds. The responses of photons relate to camouflage engineering in general. The camouflage engineering signifies the CDRI of objects against multidimensional combat backgrounds, DGTWSICBs.

Tables 2 and 3 are cited to support this review. The approach of research has also contents of experiment-based suggestions and self-cited literature of the author for the next stage practice of research and development in color engineering and camouflage engineering. The author has some self-cited-self-experimented reviews for the support of this review work mentioned in Tables 2 and 3. The author briefly reviewed in 2020, gradually self-verified and self-experimented for the support of this review article (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023c, 2023g, 2023h, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023aq, 2023au, 2023az, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bn, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023cj, 2023 cl) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023g, 2023h, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023au, 2023az, 2023bd, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bn, 2023bu, 2023cj, 2023cl; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024k, 2024l).

Abbreviations

UV-Vis-IR	Ultraviolet-visible-infrared
DGTWSICB	Dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark-woodland combat background; water-marine combat background; sand-desertland

CBs	combat background; stone-stoneland combat background; snow-snowland combat background; sky combat background; ice-iceland combat background and concrete-concreteland combat background
CDRI	Combat backgrounds Concealment, detection, recognition and identification
NIR	Near infrared
Target signature	Camouflage textiles for concealment and detection
Woodland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in woodland background such as dry leaves, green leaves, tree bark, etc.
Water/marine combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in water/marine background
Desertland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in desertland background
Stoneland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in stoneland background
Snowland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in snowland background
Sky combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in sky background
Iceland combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in iceland background
Concreteland/urban combat background	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in concreteland background
Single background camouflage	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in specific background environment-DGTWSICB
Simultaneous background camouflage	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in few background environments-DGTWSICB
Adaptive camouflage	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in few background environments-DGTWSICB in terms of chromatic replacement against combat background
Temperature adaptive camouflage	Camouflaging and detection of target signature in temperature changing environments against few background-DGTWSICB
NPND	Natural plant-based natural dyes
NSSD	Natural sand-based silicon dioxide
PCMs	Phase change materials
CBP	Carbon black pigment
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
FTIRs	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
PU	Polyurethane
PA 6,6	Polyamide 6,6
CIE	International commission on illumination
RGB	Red, green, blue
OB	Object-background
PhD	Doctor of philosophy

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-024-00182-8>.

Additional file 1: Table S1. Summarized spectral coefficients of sun radiation, CB materials and camouflage materials for design of camouflage textiles in UV-Vis-IR illumination.

Acknowledgements

Sole author, director (PhD research), director (defence project), Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist; (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; A. Hossain, A. S. Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; A. Hossain, A. K. Samanta, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023c, 2023aq; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019; M. A. Hossain et al., 2018; Samanta et al., 2016) (Hossain, 2023ak, 2023an, 2023bj, 2023cj, 2023cl) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2022; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023g, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bm, 2023bn, 2023bo, 2023bp; Hossain, 2023a; Hossain, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt, 2023bu; Hossain, 2023b; Hossain, 2023bv, 2023bw, 2023bx; Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd, 2023ce, 2023cf; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023cl, 2023cm, 2023cn; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s; Md. Anwar Hossain, 2024) Name of Father: Late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, Medical Practitioner; Permanent Residence (PR): Village: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); Nationality, National ID, Passport and Birth Registration Number: Bangladeshi, 19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, Program Name: DR213, PhD (Fashion and Textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; Lecturer on Textile Engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and the Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2024. Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) also acknowledges 'Professor Dr. Lijing Wang' (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7300-9271>) and 'Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks' (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University for their draft review of manuscript. A short summary and evidence of the Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1272255> Please visit the following link for author information about Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist; Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1> <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287> <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain> www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/JMP-7353-2023> <https://sciprofiles.com/profile/1995474>

Peer Review Process of Institutional Review Board, RMIT University, Australia

This manuscript was reviewed and passed by the two individual Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) committees of the School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University by the two individual conferences of the School of Fashion and Textiles,

RMIT University by the two individual examinations of the first milestone and second milestones under institutional prerequisites of PhD degree (fashion and textiles), RMIT University, Australia.

My PhD struggle, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and the announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Peer Review Process of Journal

In general, this manuscript has gone through the editorial review process of different journals such as *The Journal of The Textile Institute*, *Journal of Industrial Textiles*, *Scientific Report*, *Textile Research Journal*, *Color Research & Application*, *Dyes and Pigment*, *Advanced Materials*, *Advances in Material Science and Engineering-Hindawi*, *Textiles*, *Coloration Technology*, *Defence Technology*, *Journal of Material Science: Materials in Engineering from 2020 to 2024*.

Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of "Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist" on "Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds" School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anwar@yahoo.com). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

Preprint publication

The online second version on 23 October 2023 (<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2549022/v1>; <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202310.1344.v1>) and the first version on 15 February 2023 (<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2549022/v1>).

Authors' contributions

The author is self-declaring the sole-authorship of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD, Defence Scientist in terms of conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, research communications, research planning and prediction, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role in the design of research, research idea or visualization, research and innovation, drafting of the manuscript, editing of the manuscript and publication of the manuscript.

Funding

The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

Availability of data and materials

The data information generated during the manuscript drafting process is attached to this manuscript as supporting information, Table S1.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

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Received: 11 June 2024 Accepted: 17 September 2024

Published online: 05 December 2024

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